

D1.2 Robotic System Specification – design of the Sharework framework

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Executive Summary

This document describes the SHAREWORK system specifications for each use-case, starting from the requirements already identified in D1.1 “*Use cases definition, system requirements and KPIs*”. Each use case scenario description is improved with greater details on human-robot collaborative tasks and layouts are presented through 2D and 3D visualization. Furthermore, general module specifications and inter-modules dependencies are reported, also detailing the role of all modules in each use-case. In such a way, a comprehensive and deeper understanding of all SHAREWORK system components emerges from this deliverable, highlighting its main features and differences in implementation in the four use cases.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>C2I</i>	<i>Command, Control and Intelligence</i>
<i>C4I</i>	<i>Command, Control, Communications, Computers and Intelligence</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>UAS</i>	<i>Unmanned Aerial System</i>
<i>UGV</i>	<i>Unmanned Ground Vehicle</i>
<i>CPCS</i>	<i>Central Process Control System</i>
<i>NPS</i>	<i>Navigation and Perception Sensors</i>
<i>PMS</i>	<i>Process Monitoring Sensors</i>
<i>RU-V1</i>	<i>Robotic Unit Version 1</i>
<i>LfD</i>	<i>Learning from Demonstration</i>
<i>HRC</i>	<i>Human Robot Cooperation</i>
<i>AGV</i>	<i>Autonomous Guided Vehicle</i>
<i>DoF</i>	<i>Degree of Freedom</i>

1 Introduction

This document intends to describe the SHAREWORK system specifications for each use-case, starting from the requirements already identified in D1.1 “*Use cases definition, system requirements and KPIs*”. In details, use-cases layout after SHAREWORK implementation is presented through 2D and 3D visualization, both for the mock-up demonstrator and the real industrial environment, and hardware specifications are included. Workflow of different end-users’ processes is also described step by step. Temporal and spatial cooperation between operator and robot is therefore highlighted through an accurate understanding of shared workspace during the different phases of the process, as well as timing of the tasks and role of the robot / operator.

Furthermore, general module specifications and inter-modules dependencies, are reported, while the role of them in each use-case is described in details.

The document, for each application, is elaborated iteratively, firstly interacting with the End-User Project Manager and secondly with inputs and feedback of the rest of partners. Therefore, the final deliverable is agreed among all SHAREWORK partners.

2 Structure and description of contents

The four end users are addressed separately in the document. For each of them, first tasks considered in the SHAREWORK project are updated and described again. Afterwards, SHAREWORK implementation is described in details, including all the hardware specifications (e.g. robot, AGV, etc.) needed to complete tasks and fully satisfy requirements. 2D and 3D visualizations of the foreseen layout is provided to allow a better comprehension of the SHAREWORK framework integration within the industrial environment and to visualize sharing of workspace between robot and operator through different tasks. Each module is explained in the tailored use-case context to highlight its role and expected tasks.

Finally, module specifications (e.g. sensors), independently from use-case specific requirements, are reported in a final general section. Furthermore, inter-modules dependencies are explained, i.e. which inputs feed each module and, in turn, which outputs are developed.

3 System specification

3.1 GOIZPER use case

GOIZPER use case deals with the manufacturing of a servo rotary table, the PGI series, shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SERVO ROTARY TABLE – PGI series

This series comes in 5 different models of similar design and different dimensions. The SHAREWORK system will need, therefore, to provide the required flexibility in order to comply with the specific requirements, in terms of dimensions and applied torques, of each design. GOIZPER use case will focus on the three scenarios described in D1.1, which are briefly reintroduced below.

Rotary table bolts tightening

Bolt tightening is a low added value task that is currently performed manually by operators. This operation requires first to apply adhesive on the bolts, which are then inserted in the correct holes and screwed.

Figure 2. Bolts required for assembly operations

The 5 rotary table design will integrate 5 different bolts dimensions, each one with a different required torque for tightening, as described below:

- M8: 41Nm
- M10: 83Nm
- M12: 145Nm
- M14: 230Nm
- M16: 355Nm

Locking ring bolts tightening

This operation is similar to the one described above, but present a higher degree of complexity, given by the need to follow a precise locking procedure to correctly complete the task. The procedure is presented in Figure 3 and is better detailed in D1.1.

Figure 3. Locking procedure for locking ring bolts

During SHAREWORK project, we will deal with 2 different designs of locking ring, each one with different bolts sizes and required locking torques, as described below:

- M8: 20Nm – 41Nm
- M10: 40Nm – 83Nm

Cam followers visual inspection

The quality inspection of the assembled product is a key operation that is performed at the end of the assembly process. The operator rotates the input shaft while observing the motion of the followers through two circular openings. The followers are supposed to rotate as shown in Figure 4. More details are provided in D1.1.

Figure 4: Cam followers rotation for visual inspection

Similarly to the other two scenarios, different design of the rotary table require different torque to rotate the input shaft, going up to 200Nm for the biggest size.

3.1.1 Use case layout

Goizper assembly plant (Figure 5) is a 180m² room comprehensive of 6 workstation (in blue) and is divided into 5 squared areas of 6x6m² by concrete columns. The overall plant layout is flexible and, depending on the ShareWork developments, could be rearranged to allow a more efficient implementation of the robotic system.

Figure 5. GOIZPER assembly plant layout

The future view of GOIZPER towards human-robot collaboration in their assembly facility is to implement a mobile robotic system, which can move between workstations and cooperate with all workers in hard and repetitive tasks. To push the ShareWork system towards this view, the demo scenario will reproduce one 6x6m² area between four columns, comprehensive of two workstation, one mobile robotic platform and, possibly, one AGV, certified for collaborative environments, to move the robot between the two workstations. Mobility of the robot is an important requirement for GOIZPER and will be addressed in the scenario, it is currently under discussion the implementation of an AGV or a simpler mobile platform that operators can move in the working area. This layout is presented in Figure 6 (2D top view) and Figure 7 (3D view).

Figure 6. GOIZPER demo layout

Figure 7. GOIZPER demo layout 3D view

At the corner of the demo area, representing the concrete columns in Goizper plant, are mounted 4 cameras, which allow a complete vision of the scenario at any time. The view from the four cameras is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Cameras view in GOIZPER demo case

The four cameras will have a complete view of the demo scenario, being able to address the human-robot cooperation in both workstation, depending on the robot position, and also during robot motion on the mobile platform.

Sections below present the GOIZPER step-by-step approach in the three scenarios considering an AGV is implemented to move the robot. In case a mobile platform is used instead, motion of the robot to the hydraulic table will be performed by the operator, resulting in a small increase of the total time required to complete the collaborative task.

The time required for each task is an estimation based on the measurements performed by GOIZPER and presented in D1.1, where the total time spent performing the tasks during a complete rotary table assembly was indicated. Here, instead, each single robot task is considered.

3.1.2 Bolts tightening workflow

Table 1. Step-by-step process in GOIZPER use-case: 1st scenario

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT	TIME [s]
1	Request the robot at the workstation	Receive request	5
2	Put adhesive on bolts and insert them (part 1)	Move to workstation	30
3		Move to rest position	5
4	Mount correct tool on end effector	Rest position	60
5	Select tool program for specific bolts		30

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT	TIME [s]
6	Put adhesive on bolts and insert them (part 2)	Identify and screw bolts up to the specified torque	60
7			180
8	Get ready for next assembly task	Signal correct operations/errors to operator	5
9	Move on to following tasks	Move to another table	-
COMPLETE PROCESS			375

Human-robot collaboration in this task takes place on the rotary table. The operator inserts the bolts in their holes while the robot screws them. This operation is performed at the same time by the operator and the robot, therefore, the robot motion planning becomes essential to avoid collisions and dangerous behaviour during task execution. The robot will be able to recognize which bolts are already positioned and start screwing them, as there is no predetermined order in this task. Force measurement and control will allow the robot to apply the correct torque on the bolts

The workstation will be divided into two areas: on one side, where the rotary table is positioned, the workspace is shared between human and robot, as the operator will position the bolts while the robot screws them. On the other side, only the human will operate when he has completed the bolts insertion, while the robot in parallel completes the screwing task. In red is indicated the robot-only workspace.

3.1.3 Locking ring bolts tightening workflow

Table 2. Step-by-step process in GOIZPER use-case: 2nd scenario

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT	TIME [s]
1	Request the robot at the workstation	Receive request	5

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT	TIME [s]
2	Prepare and position the locking ring on its fixation	Move to workstation	20
3		Move to rest position	5
4	Mount correct tool on end effector	Rest position	60
5	Select tool program for specific bolts		30
6	Perform other assembly tasks in parallel with the robot (shared workspace)	Following a pre-determined pattern, tight the screw at half torque	80
7		Repeat the same pattern and tight up to full torque	150
8		Signal correct operations/errors to operator	5
9	Proceed to next task	Move to another assembly station	-
COMPLETE PROCESS			355

This task is similar to the previous one, but collaboration is less predominant. This is true because the operator will need to position all the bolts before the robot starts to screw them. The robot will need to identify the bolts with precision, due to the narrow space available between the bolts and the shaft and communicate with the operator, through a dedicated user interface on a screen or wearables, in case any error occurs.

In this task, the robot and the human will work in parallel. The small area of shared workspace indicates a possible collaboration in case the robot will signal any error that requires human intervention (e.g., a bolt not well positioned or tightened), through a dedicated user interface on a screen or wearables, otherwise, the operator will work on the rotary table on one side of the workstation while the robot automatically screws the locking ring bolts on the other side.

3.1.4 Visual inspection workflow

Table 3. Step-by-step process in GOIZPER use-case: 3rd scenario

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT	TIME [s]
1	Request the robot at the workstation	Receive request	5
2	Mount input shaft rotation bar	Move to workstation	20
3		Move to rest position	5
4	Mount correct tool on end effector	Rest position	60
5	Move in front of cam openings	Identify and grab input shaft	10
6	Guide robot shaft rotation (e.g.: slow down, stop, invert rotation, speed up) through verbal/gesture communication	Rotate input shaft at required speed, up to 360° rotation of shaft	600
7	Check rotation of cam followers through openings		
8	Finalize inspection	Signal end of 360° rotation	5
9	Next task	Move to another station	-
COMPLETE PROCESS			705

In this task human-robot collaboration is present mainly in terms of communication. The robot will need to follow the human commands with precision as it rotates the rotary table shaft. No physical interaction is foreseen between human and robot. The human will provide indications to the robot through specific arms and hands gestures that will communicate when the robot needs to start/stop rotation and increase/decrease rotational speed. Force control on the robot will be essential to guarantee a smooth rotation of the shaft at the required speed so that the operator can check the correct rotation of the cam followers. Human tracking and natural communication will be the centre modules to enable this task.

Human and robot will be positioned at different sides of the workstation without the need to physically interact. Depending on how the gesture for communication with the robot are defined, the operator might need to touch the bar used for shaft rotation or, similarly, to enter the shared workspace to give the robot the stop signal.

3.1.5 Modules involvement

Indicate here all the modules involved in the use case and their role

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#1	CNR	The module will provide a virtualization (i.e., an abstract representation in the Knowledge Base) of the working cell, i.e., of the overall workflow, the possible actions the human can do (described above) and the distribution of elements (position of tools, sensors, types of structure...). All the above information are expected to be defined by a production engineer. Dynamically, the module will keep updated the KB according to the actual operational context.
#2	RWTH	A general semantic cognition method will be developed, which enables the vision network to detect certain objects and classify them using a unique identifier. In case of the Goizper use-case the network will be trained to detect all relevant dynamic objects: Human shapes, robots, bolts, the electrical screw driver, rotary tables and tools. Further, the static environment will be clustered and classified in rotary tables, work benches and general room features. All operations are performed and forwarded with the required accuracy to be used in the high-level tasks.

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#3	EURECAT	A human tracking algorithm will be developed to provide information about the workers over time. That means that a skeleton representing the human pose will be obtained as well as the human position within the environment. This module must be able to detect not only the position and pose but also if more than one operator is in the station. The input of this module will be given by a set of sensors placed appropriately around the workplace. The output of this module will be used to define safe working zones for the robot and an input to primitives to recognize human tasks.
#4	TUDA	The Motion Primitives Learning will be a task-agnostic tool. The module will be able to segment monitored operator trajectories and build generalizable motion primitives from this segmented trajectories. In the GOIZPER use case, the module will be applied in order to extract the primitives of the user operators performing bolt tightening and assembly task. Together with the classification module, the module will help to identify operators actions.
#5	EURECAT	This module will develop the necessary algorithms to interpret data coming from the workspace monitoring and cognition in order to identify the task that the worker is executing and to provide this information to the dynamic task planning and scheduling algorithm. That means that the output from Primitives Learning and Environment Cognition will be used as input to create a solution which is able to do task identification.
#6	CNR-ISTC	<p>The module will dynamically generate a task plan in order to assign production tasks among the human operator and the robot. Then, it will monitor tasks execution and, in case of need, it will adapt execution and/or revise tasks assignment in order to maintain safety and increase efficacy.</p> <p>The probabilistic reasoning sub-module will use some of the pieces of information saved in the Knowledge Base about the actual status of the system (the inputs) to derive decision values and predictions (the outputs) that will be used as triggers for the main planner. Furthermore, the parallel planning feature with its according smooting algorithms will ensure at each time step that a valid plan is available for the actors.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#7	CNR-STIIMA	<p>The online/offline motion planner will be a task-agnostic tool. In other words, once the digital model of each task will be available, the modules will act in order to ease and optimize the robot plans given the task constraints and goals.</p> <p>The offline motion planner will ensure the intuitive easiness granting collision free and ergonomics trajectories. The online motion planner will allow the reaction to the dynamic environment.</p> <p>The online re-planning is strongly constrained in the GOIZPER use case, where the movements are strongly synchronized between human operator and robot. Therefore, an adaptive, safe and fuzzy velocity tuning is expected to be the most important reaction strategies in the use-case.</p>
#8	TUDA	<p>The Learning from Demonstration (LfD) is an alternative way of path planning. In LfD, the operator could teach the robot the correct path to follow and robot would build motion primitives in order to follow correctly taught motions.</p> <p>In the GOIZPER use case, the module could be applied in order to learn in a teach mode those trajectories that are hard to plan by classic offline planners.</p>
#9	LMS	<p>An Augmented Reality application will be implemented for providing useful information to the worker for the execution workflow and for the robot's activities. Human operator will be able to interact with the robot and the rest of the system in two ways. The first one is directly through the AR application with some interactable holograms presented in the field of view of the worker. In addition, Voice commands and sound alerts will be provided also for making the interaction more natural.</p>
#10	FRAUNHOFER	<p>Motion of the robot will be managed to keep the operator, at any moment, safe. The moving robot will be slower when working next to or approaching a human avoiding any collision and specially when it is performing the screwing as it is a more dangerous task, due to the operator moving his hands close to the robot screwdriver.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#11	RWTH	The TCP vision system will be integrated in the overall vision network of module #2 to enable further surveillance of the workspace. The module is projected to detect the position of the cam followers and therefore allow further decision making during their adjustment operations. Further, this module adapts the safety system based on module #10 onto the local robot frame to improve the safety of the human worker.
#12	INTRA	This module will be generic and applicable to all use cases. In particular this module will deliver a toolset for data security. Each use case will be able to select and apply the useful and relevant components. The toolset will provide both data security Policies and Practices as well as a list of software libraries and tools.
#13	FRAUNHOFER	The system can check if the operator is in a bad ergonomic posture and provide this information to the worker so that he/she can correct the posture in future. The data recorded by the cameras is sensible data as it has private information of the workers so it has to be protected using methodologies from module 12. Information can be provided as overall analysis figures, specifying which part of the task the user can improve his/her pose
#14	LMS	An application for training new operators based on AR technology will be demonstrated in this use case. This application will be deployed offline. The new worker will be on the workstation and the assembly steps will be presented to him in form of holograms. Intuitive symbols will make the learning process faster and easier.

3.2 ALSTOM use case

Among all the working stations described in the deliverable D1.1, the Alstom use case within Sharework will be focused on station 3. It is the most interesting one as several operations are performed in this station.

As a reminder from D1.1, there are some on-going operations that are performed in station 3:

- Contour marking: position metallic part + pen marking + remove metallic part
- Surface cleaning
- Sillicon application
- Sillicon spreading
- Metalic part positioning
- Close station fixtures
- Riveting

- Quality inspection

These operations will be either performed by the human or the robot as they are specific tasks but the overall scenario in the Alstom manufacturing process will be collaborative. A cobot will be selected with a minimum payload of 10kg, since the riveting tool weights already 5kg and there is also the need for an adapted gripper to be able to change between tools. The cobot will be mounted on an industrial AGV, certified for collaborative environments. This will give the robot movement flexibility around the workstation and it will be able to react and adapt to the human on-going task. The possibility to get ahead to the humans' needs and the fact that the human is not forced to move around the robot will help in increasing operators acceptance. The contour marking operation will be removed as the silicon application will be performed with the robot, so the limits will be detected through computer vision. The surface cleaning and silicon spreading are easier tasks to humans so the operator will continue doing them. The latter will also position the structure and close fixtures before placing the rivets into the holes. The robot will perform the riveting as it is a heavy repetitive and not ergonomic task and the operator will check the result of the riveting as a quality inspection task.

3.2.1 Use case layout

The demonstrator will be equal to the actual working zone, taking only the station 3. The dimensions and passage areas will be of the same size in order to correctly reflect the reality. A 2D view of the layout is shown in the figure below.

Figure 9. 2D view of the ALSTOM use-case layout

While the final 3D view of the environment is represented in the following picture.

Figure 10. 3D view of the ALSTOM use-case layout

As far as vision system is concerned, the ideal situation would be placing four cameras, one at each corner of the workstation, to have a complete view of all the scenario. However, this is not a possible option due to physical restrictions. As an alternative, two cameras will be placed on the wall at 3 metres, at the top corners of the workstation. These two cameras will provide an almost global vision of the whole scenario. However, as the operator can be working in all corners of the table, there will be blind zones. It is for this reason that two more cameras will be added in two corners just behind the table in the opposite side of the wall. This fact will allow a complete tracking of the whole scenario without blind zones. The view from the four cameras is presented in the following figure.

Figure 11. View from each of the 4 cameras

3.2.2 Workflow

In the following table each task is shortly described and the expected time spent for each specific task.

Table 4. step-by-step process in ALSTOM use-case

STEP	OPERATOR	TIME [s]	ROBOT	TIME [s]
1	Communicate task to robot	5	Receive communication	-
2	Position structure 0-3	90		
3	Position structure 1-2	90	Detect structure type	1
4	Clean surface 0	20	Change tool: silicone gun	30
5	Clean surface 1	20		
6	Clean surface 2	20	Apply silicone 0	20
7	Clean surface 3	20	Apply silicone 1	20
8	Spread silicone 0	60	Apply silicone 2	20
9	Spread silicone 1	60	Apply silicone 3	20
10	Spread silicone 2	60	Change tool: riveting tool	30
11	Spread silicone 3	60		
12	Position structure 0-1	40		
13	Insert rivets 0	30		
14	Insert rivets 1	30		
15	Close station fixtures 0-1	45		
16	Position structure 2-3	40	Riveting 0	65
17	Insert rivets 2	30	Riveting 1	65
18	Insert rivets 3	30		
19	Close station fixtures 2-3	45		
20	Quality inspection 0	6	Riveting 2	65
21	Quality inspection 1	6	Riveting 3	65
22	Quality inspection 2	6		
23	Quality inspection 3	6		

Step 1, communication with the robot, might happen at a different step or multiple times, due to the flexibility allowed in ALSTOM use case.

Note that the numbers refer to a specific corner of the table, as most operations are repeated for each corner. The following figure shows the corner distribution of the workstation

Figure 12. scheme of the workstation

3.2.3 Modules involvement

In this paragraph, the role of each module in the ALSTOM use-case is described.

Table 5. module involvement in ALSTOM use-case

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#1	CNR	The module will provide a virtualization (i.e., an abstract representation in the Knowledge Base) of the working cell, i.e., of the overall workflow, the possible actions the human can do (described above) and the distribution of elements (position of tools, sensors, types of structure...). In case of the Alstom use-case, information about door and window frames will be included, as well as tools and instructions for riveting and silicone application. All the above information are expected to be defined by a production engineer. Dynamically, the module will keep updated the KB according to the actual operational context.
#2	RWTH	A general semantic cognition method will be developed, which enables the vision network to detect certain objects and classify them using a unique identifier. In case of the Alstom use-case the network will be trained to detect all relevant dynamic objects: Human shapes, robots, door and window frames, rivets (including their mounting state), the silicon gun and riveting tools. Further, the static environment will be clustered and classified in work tables, work benches and general room features. All operations are performed and forwarded with the required accuracy to be used in the high-level tasks. The Alstom use-case may require additional emphasise on high resolution detection, including methods to deal with additional load on the communication system and during data processing.

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#3	EURECAT	<p>A human tracking algorithm will be developed to provide information about the workers during the operations. That means that a skeleton representing the human pose will be obtained as well as the human position within the environment. This module must be able to detect not only the position and pose but also if more than one operator is in the station. The input of this module will be given by the four cameras placed in the workplace. The output of this module will be used to define safe working zones for the robot and an input to primitives to recognize human tasks. As far as ALSTOM use-case is concerned, human-tracking algorithm will be finely tuned considering the impossibility to place cameras in all the corners of the workstation.</p>
#4	TUDA	<p>The Motion Primitives Learning will be a task-agnostic tool. The module will be able to segment monitored operator trajectories and build generalizable motion primitives from this segmented trajectories.</p> <p>In the ALSTOM use case, the module needs to builds motion primitives on the actions that the operator performs such as cleaning surface, spreading silicone, positioning rivets or fixing structure. This information will be useful for classification of the operator tasks but also to plan safe robot motions.</p>
#5	EURECAT	<p>This module will develop the necessary algorithms to interpret data coming from the workspace monitoring and cognition in order to identify the task that the worker is executing and to provide this information to the dynamic task planning and scheduling algorithm. That means that the output from Primitives Learning and Environment Cognition will be used as input to create a solution which is able to do task identification.</p> <p>In the ALSTOM use-case, the system should be able to recognize operators cleaning the surface, spreading silicone, positioning rivets and fixing structure. This will enable a close human-robot cooperation.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#6	CNR-ISTC	<p>The module will dynamically generate a task plan in order to assign production tasks among the human operator and the robot. Then, it will monitor tasks execution and, in case of need, it will adapt execution and/or revise tasks assignment in order to maintain safety and increase efficacy. The probabilistic reasoning sub-module will use some of the pieces of information saved in the Knowledge Base about the actual status of the system (the inputs) to derive decision values and predictions (the outputs) that will be used as triggers for the main planner. Furthermore, the parallel planning feature with its according smooting algorithms will ensure at each time step that a valid plan is available for the actors.</p> <p>In ALSTOM use-case task dynamic planning is relevant since the same task are performed in each of the 4 corner, but the order of the corners can be modified any time.</p>
#7	CNR-STIIMA	<p>The online/offline motion planner will be a task-agnostic tool. In other words, one the digital model of each task will be available, the modules will act in order to ease and optimize the robot plans given the task constraints and goals.</p> <p>The offline motion planner will ensure the intuitive easiness granting collision free and ergonomics trajectories. The online motion planner will allow the reaction to the dynamic environment.</p> <p>In the ALSTOM environment, the robot tasks are almost all constrained in the Cartesian space, therefore the room for online re-planning is limited. Furthermore, the synchronization between human operator and robot is still to be further investigated. Therefore, an adaptive, safe and fuzzy velocity tuning is expected to be the most important reaction strategies in the use-case.</p>
#8	TUDA	<p>The Learning from Demonstration (LfD) is an alternative way of path planning. In LfD, the operator could teach the robot the correct path to follow and robot would build motion primitives in order to follow correctly taught motions. In ALSTOM use case, robot tasks such as sillicon appliance and riveting can be easily taught using LfD.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#9	LMS	In this use case, an application for tablets will facilitate the communication between the operator and the robotic system. The operator can give confirmation to the robot to perform the next scheduled operation, e.g. riveting in ALSTOM use-case, or he can check the workflow in a screen GUI.
#10	FRAUNHOFER	In order to be compliant with safety standards, the motion of the robot will be slower when working next to or approaching a human avoiding any collision. In the ALSTOM use-case this countermeasure will be implemented specially when it is performing the riveting, as it is a more dangerous task.
#11	RWTH	The TCP vision system will be integrated in the overall vision network of module #2 to enable further surveillance of the workspace. As far as ALSTOM use-case is concerned, the system is projected to improve the reliability of rivet state detection and enable the silicone spreading by measuring the proper distance to the frame boundaries. Further, this module adapts the safety system based on module #10 onto the local robot frame to improve the safety of the human worker, especially, during the riveting process.
#12	INTRA	This module will be generic and applicable to all use cases. In particular this module will deliver a toolset for data security. Each use case will be able to select and apply the useful and relevant components. The toolset will provide both data security Policies and Practices as well as a list of software libraries and tools.
#13	FRAUNHOFER	The system can check if the operator is in a bad ergonomic posture and provide this information to the worker for him to be able to correct its posture in future. In the ALSTOM use-case, silicone spreading and fixing of the structure would be focused to improve ergonomics for the operator. Information can be provided as overall analysis figures, specifying which part of the task the user can improve his/her pose
#14	LMS	Since the number of components is small and geometries of parts are not very complex operator training through AR seems not to have added value in the ALSTOM use-case.

3.3 NISSAN use case

NISSAN use case emphasizes on the passenger door assembly on vehicle cab besides a series of tasks at the pick-up's bed. These tasks require manipulation of large objects (e.g. passenger doors) as well as smaller components (e.g. nuts, electrical harness, etc.) demanding higher dexterity. The vehicle is located on a moving conveyor that travels with a constant speed of 3.35 meters per minute. During assembly, operator follows the chassis and performs all the tasks on the moving vehicle. As it concerns feeding, two conveyors feed the front and rear doors on every cycle. These two conveyors are positioned on each side of the assembly line and are partially separated by two fences that secure human absence during the transportation of new doors. For door manipulation, the operators use an assistant hoist device to manually guide the doors to their mounting positions. This device carries the weight of the door while the operator adjusts the positioning of it.

Figure 13. NISSAN Current assembly line

SHAREWORK's envisaged solution replaces the hoist assistant device with an overhead high payload articulated robot arm. The robot arm is mounted on ceiling rail/ gantry system and follows the cab at the conveyor's speed. This configuration reduces the need for high reachability robot. Moreover, the current operator's working area is not affected by additional equipment leaving free space for his/her movements. SHAREWORK solution allocates non-ergonomic tasks or tasks that do not require high dexterity to the robot arm. In contrast, the operator is responsible for more delicate or dexterous processes (e.g. final door positioning, pre-setting of nuts, connecting of door harness, etc.). Finally, the integration of a robot arm and complete automation of a series of manual tasks leads to parallel execution of processes thus cycle time reduction. In detail, the transportation of doors from feeding area to the vehicle is automated and does not need human intervention. In parallel, operator is able to perform assembly tasks at the vehicle's bed for balancing the whole assembly line. The envisioned solution is depicted on the following figure.

Figure 14. SHAREWORK envisioned solution for NISSAN Use Case

The layout is based on the current assembly line configuration and dimensions. It uses the same door feeding systems, conveyor line and manual tools leading to easier implementation of SHAREWORK. A series of perception and safety devices are used to ensure safe Human-Robot Interaction and Collaboration. Those systems monitor operator's position and actions to avoid and minimize any risk of collision or injury. Apart from operator tracking, during operation, the position of the cab is defined by perception devices. More specifically, a vision system is used to recognize the chassis' location in combination with an encoder device that tracks the position of the conveyor updating the vehicle coordinates. Except from aforementioned technologies, robot trajectory and tasks are also coordinated by operator himself /herself through direct and natural human system interaction. More information regarding the modules for perception, safety and interaction of operator with the system follow on section 3.3.3.

3.3.1 Use case layout

SHAREWORK's modules and technologies will be developed, implemented and validated in demonstration layouts that will be integrated within the project. Those demonstration layouts will replicate the current assembly line's dimensions and characteristics proving applicability of project's outcomes to the existing end-user's infrastructure. For the NISSAN use-case, two demonstration hybrid assembly cells will be implemented within the project period, namely:

- Mock-up demonstrator
- Industrial demonstrator

Both demonstrators will be described in details in the next two paragraphs.

3.3.1.1 NISSAN use case industrial demonstrator

This demonstrator will be implemented at the end-user's premises and will be used for the integration and validation of mature SHAREWORK technologies. This demonstration layout will replicate the dimensions of the current assembly line. Moreover, it will be parted by resources same or similar to existing ones referring to the vehicle conveyor line as well as passenger door feeding system (refer to Figure 14). An overhead rail/ gantry system will be used for mounting the robot in ceiling configuration. The robot arm will have access on the door feeding system and will transport doors to the vehicle area. The integration of the rail system leads to a total number of degrees of freedom (DoF) that equals to 7. The one extra DoF, that refers to the gantry, will be used to synchronize robot with the moving vehicle. The remaining 6 DoFs, that come from the robot arm, will be used for achieving the required relevant positioning of the doors in respect to the chassis, besides navigating into the workspace. In contrast with current site, operators are not obliged to approach the feeding area since relevant tasks are automated. They will work next to the vehicle, as illustrated, and will cooperate with the robot arm during door positioning and assembly to the cab. Subsequently, fences can be removed, as operator's position in the layout will be constantly monitored by perception and safety devices.

Figure 15. NISSAN use case industrial demonstrator top view and zones

3.3.1.2 NISSAN use-case mock-up demonstrator

This demonstrator will be used for the preliminary implementation of SHAREWORK modules. The dimensions of this layout are equal to the ones of the current assembly line and subsequently to those of the industrial demonstrator. This cell will be established at LMS premises for reducing the technology implementation time during development phases and it is actually a fundamental version of the industrial demonstrator. There is a series of layout resources that can be optimized in terms of cost and complexity without affecting the applicability of SHAREWORK modules besides their validation in respect to defined KPIs. In detail, the passenger door feeding conveyor system is replaced by two door fixtures. The fixtures positioning in the layout makes the door picking points identical or same as the ones of the industrial demonstrator and assembly line. Moreover, the vehicle conveyor line is not essential for developing and testing all relevant to the case modules, therefore the robot rail/ gantry is not required as well. The rail will be replaced by an overhead pedestal that positions the robot in the same spot with the axis of the rail system.

Figure 16. NISSAN use case mock-up demonstrator

The dimension and working zones of the mock-up demonstrator are illustrated on 17. The advantage of those optimizations at early project stages permit rapid implementation of a cell identical to the final one in the most cost-effective way that is used for the development and testing of modules.

Figure 17. NISSAN use case mock-up demonstrator dimensions and zones

3.3.1.3 Demonstrator comparison

As described, both demonstrators are structured based on the current assembly line for easier applicability of SHAREWORK in the use case. The implementation of the mock-up demonstrator makes possible testing of the developed modules in early project stages providing feedback to development teams based on real scenario. Interaction modules, safety systems and perception devices will be implemented on the industrial demonstrator after their optimization and physical testing in the mock-up layout. Regarding human perception and safety, the following figure illustrates that experiments in static vehicle, thus robot mount, do not affect the detection methods since assembly process and workflow remains the same

(refer to 3.3.2). Considering that most of the modules will be mature enough to their final version, towards the integration of the demonstrator in end-user's premises, vehicle following using the rail system will be the only technology to be optimized.

Figure 18. Comparison of conceptual human perception system between two demonstrators

3.3.2 Workflow

The workflow of use-case after Implementation of SHAREWORK is the same in both demonstrators. In contrast with the current work flow, there is parallel execution of tasks since a series of them is completely automated. Additionally, there is close human robot collaboration in tasks where the demanded dexterity surpasses the robot capabilities. Specifically, HRC is used for the final positioning of the door on the chassis.

Table 6. step-by-step process in NISSAN use-case

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT	TIME [s]
1	Hood sealant application (HOOD area)	Approaching conveyor	6
2		Front door picking	5
3	Approaching front door assembly spot	Signaling operator to approach front door assembly spot	-
		Approaching vehicle	6
4	Door harness connection	-Vehicle following -Collaboration with operator for door position fine-tuning via manual guidance	15
5	Pre-setting of nuts		12
6	Grasping of HCT		3
7	Fastener tightening		6
8	Grasping of HCT		3
9	Nut tightening		12
10	Setting of channels and plugs at side bed (Part 1)		Approaching conveyor
11	Approaching back door assembly spot	Back door picking	5
12		Signaling operator to approach front door assembly spot	-
		Approaching vehicle	6

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT	TIME [s]
13	Door harness connection	-Vehicle following -Collaboration with operator for door position fine-tuning via manual guidance	15
14	Pre-setting of nuts		12
15	Grasping of HCT		3
16	Fastener tightening		6
17	Grasping of HCT		3
18	Nut tightening		12
19	Setting of channels and plugs at side bed (Part 2)		23
Complete Cycle			159

A more detailed presentation of aforementioned tasks and how SHAREWORK modules are applied on the use case follows:

Table 7. SHAREWORK enhanced NISSAN case key processes

Picking of passenger doors from feeding conveyor

This task is completely automated and does not require any human involvement. The robot approaches the door feeding area and picks the corresponding door. During this robotic task operator executes a series of manual tasks either on the vehicle's hood or side bed. The door's position is tracked by perception devices of module #2 and robot trajectory is updated via module #7. In parallel in case of human infringement inside robot or feeding area module #7 ensures collision avoidance via module #3 human detection.

Robot approaches vehicle

After door picking an automated task follows. In detail, the robot brings the picked door near the vehicle. The final robot waypoint is defined after detecting the location of vehicle's chassis via perception systems of module #2. For the final version of the demonstrator, the latest waypoint coordinates are updated by conveyor line's encoder thus the robot follows the vehicle. The movement is achieved by gantry/ rail mount movement. In case of detected human presence by module #3 robot's trajectory is updated by module #7.

Door position fine-tuning via HRC

The final positioning of the doors on vehicle's chassis is achieved through HRC. Operator sets the robot in manual guidance mode and leads the door to its final position for fastening. As soon as the position is achieved and manual guidance mode is disabled, the robot follows the vehicle maintaining the fine-tuned relevant door-vehicle positioning. For enabling manual guidance mode, the operator uses manual press buttons located on the gripper frame. In this task, module #8 and #7 work in parallel. Process status and valuable for human worker data are available to him/her via module #9.

Manual Assembly tasks

During this set of tasks, operator is responsible for electrical harness connection besides several fastening operations. In parallel, the robot arm carries the weight of the door and follows the vehicle till securing torque is applied to all fasteners. As soon as the door is assembled the robot moves to the feeding conveyor area to bring the next door. A serious aspect to be considered in those tasks is ergonomics, that is evaluated by module #13. In case of any unexpected event, modules #3, #2, #7, #9 and #10 ensure human operator's safety, awareness and comfort.

3.3.3 Modules involvement

In the following table the role of each module in NISSAN use-case is described.

Table 8. modules involvement in NISSAN use-case

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#1	CNR	The module will provide a virtualization (i.e., an abstract representation in the Knowledge Base) of the working cell, i.e., of the overall workflow, the possible actions the human can do (described above) and the distribution of elements (position of tools, sensors, types of structure, etc.). All the above information is expected to be defined by a production engineer. Dynamically, the module will keep updated the KB according to the actual operational context.

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#2	RWTH	<p>A general semantic cognition method will be developed, which enables the vision network to detect certain objects and classify them using a unique identifier.</p> <p>Within the Nissan use-case, the network will be trained to detect all relevant dynamic objects: human shapes, robots, chassis and doors. Furthermore, the static environment will be clustered and classified in conveyor section, feeding conveyor and room features. All operations are performed and forwarded with the required accuracy to be used in the high-level tasks.</p>
#3	EURECAT	<p>A human tracking algorithm will be developed to provide information about the workers over time. That means that a skeleton representing the human pose will be obtained as well as the human position within the environment. This module must be able to detect not only the position and pose but also if more than one operator is in the station. The input of this module will be given by a set of sensors placed appropriately around the workplace. The output of this module will be used to define safe working zones for the robot and an input to primitives to recognize human tasks.</p> <p>The main problem this module will face in the NISSAN use-case will be human occlusions. It is important to define sensor positions so that the operator is never located in a blind zone for all cameras as this may mean that some specific actions will be difficult to track. To solve this issue a specific camera may be placed in the robot to track not only the body but also the hands.</p>
#4	TUDA	<p>The Motion Primitives Learning will be a task-agnostic tool. The module will be able to segment monitored operator trajectories and build generalizable motion primitives from this segmented trajectories.</p> <p>In the NISSAN use case, the module needs to build probabilistic motion primitives that could inform the robot's motion planners what is the human's workspace. Since the operator is continuously moving, this Motion Primitives integration in the Path Planning will ensure safety during all the tasks in the current shared workspace.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#5	EURECAT	<p>This module will develop the necessary algorithms to interpret data coming from the workspace monitoring and cognition in order to identify the task that the worker is executing and to provide this information to the dynamic task planning and scheduling algorithm. That means that the output from Primitives Learning and Environment Cognition will be used as input to create a solution which is able to do task identification.</p> <p>In NISSAN use-case, system is supposed to be able to identify several tasks, such as hood sealant application, door harness connection, nut tightening, etc.</p>
#6	CNR-ISTC	<p>In the NISSAN use-case no high-level planning will be needed as the sequence of actions is very clear and must be followed as given and within the given time intervals.</p>
#7	CNR-STIIMA	<p>The online/offline motion planner will be a task-agnostic tool. In other words, once the digital model of each task will be available, the modules will act in order to ease and optimize the robot plans given the task constraints and goals.</p> <p>The offline motion planner will ensure the intuitive easiness granting collision free and ergonomics trajectories. The online motion planner will allow the reaction to the dynamic environment according to the data coming from the tracking system.</p> <p>In the NISSAN environment, the robot dexterity and manipulability will be of utmost importance. Indeed, the object to be manipulated together with the grasping system displays a large footprint with respect to the robot dimension. Therefore, online re-planning may be difficult due to the cluttered operative scene. Therefore, an adaptive, safe and fuzzy velocity tuning is expected to be the most important reaction strategies in the use-case.</p> <p>According to the vision system information, online planning could be useful for the tracking and the minimisation of the gap between the car and the door fixtures.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#8	TUDA	<p>The Learning from Demonstration (LfD) is an alternative way of path planning. In LfD, the operator could teach the robot the correct path to follow and robot would build motion primitives in order to follow correctly taught motions.</p> <p>In the NISSAN use case, the LfD could be applied as an alternative path planner on which the robot is taught by manual guidance the correct path to follow and the robot imitates and improves his motion until the door is correctly fixed.</p>
#9	LMS	<p>An Augmented Reality application to inform operator about robot activities and system behaviour will be applied also in NISSAN use-case. Apart from simple information regarding the process, e.g. a signal when the door is picked by the robot, the goal is to increase general human awareness for preventing hazard situations in human robot shared workspace and ergonomic issues from bad postures.</p>
#10	FRAUNHOFER	<p>The robot must operate with a safe velocity while moving in the collaborative area. There must be a force control implemented in the robotic system in case of an unexpected contact between human and robot. For the manual guiding of the robot by the worker there must be a two-hand operation implemented. The dimension of the framework for linear axis has to be taken into account the guidelines for escape routes.</p>
#11	RWTH	<p>The TCP vision system will be integrated in the overall vision network of module #2 to enable further surveillance of the workspace. As far as NISSAN use-case is concerned, the system is projected to improve the reliability of surveillance of the human worker inside the car during mounting operations. Further, this module adapts the safety system based on module #10 onto the local robot frame to improve the safety of the human worker.</p>
#12	INTRA	<p>This module will be generic and applicable to all use cases. In particular this module will deliver a toolset for data security. Each use case will be able to select and apply the useful and relevant components. The toolset will provide both data security Policies and Practices as well as a list of software libraries and tools.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#13	FRAUNHOFER	The system can check if the operator is in a bad ergonomic and assist him/her with improvements. This would comprise of providing short term and long term information to the worker for hi/her to be able to correct their posture in future. In Nissan use cases, the restricted field of view and latency in data input from posture information etc would be challenging aspect to resolve in order to help improve overall system ergonomics
#14	LMS	Interactive training procedure will be facilitated by an AR application. A process walkthrough will be provided to a new worker, taking the advantage of augmented information that can be presented on top of the real workstation. In NISSAN use-case, training through AR seems promising to facilitate and speed up the door connection to the chassis, both for mechanical and electrical connections.

3.4 CEMBRE use case

The two main areas of CEMBRE current shopfloor for the assembly of pallets and fixtures in Load/Unload Station (LUS) are:

- the transporter pallet buffer, where pallets are stored and moved, when needed, to the LUS;
- the CNC machines, where the pallets are moved to perform the machining operations.

In this use-case, SHAREWORK implementation foresees the creation of a logistic station for the main assembly of the pallets and the integration of robots at the LUS in order to ease and speed up some operations currently performed manually by the operator. At logistic stations, robot and operator will perform in close collaboration assembly of pallets, namely a set of tasks such as moving / holding parts, screw/unscrew, assemble parts and perform quality check. Therefore, in this phase of the process is foreseen the introduction of lightweight cobots and medium payload robots, since there is no need to perform heavy task. They will be mounted on an AGV to allow flexibility and mobility around the workstation, as well as to transport items between LUS and logistics station.

At the LUS, a medium-high collaborative robot will handle and assemble zero-point fixtures (ZPP) with pre-assembled items. In particular, robot will perform the following task:

- Movement of metal plates to the pallet;
- Insert, open and close hydraulic fixtures;
- Perform quality inspection on the pallet.

The redesign of the assembly workspace and the introduction of a safe and efficient human-robot cooperation will lead to reduction of cycle time and increase of final quality, as well as improvement of operators working conditions.

3.4.1 Use case layout

The factory layout is shown in Figure 20, while some photos of the plant are shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Photos of the plant, with the LUS position highlight

LOGISTIC
STATION

Figure 20. CEMBRE Layout. The assembly of the pallets will be at the logistic station, while the loading and unloading will be at the LUS. The transportation of the items will be done through a mobile robot.

Figure 21. LUS position with respect to the FSM layout

Two stations will be designed, built and deployed within ShareWork. First, logistics stations will enable a full-immersive human-robot cooperative assembly station. Second, a Smart robotized LUS (loading and un-loading station) will exploit high-payload robots in collaboration with a human. The layout and main features of each station are described in the next two paragraphs.

3.4.1.1 Use case layout: Logistic Station

Focusing on the logistic station, the design assumptions are:

- The logistic station should be extremely flexible;
- The income/outcome items will be to be assembled/disassembled to/from a «zero-point plate» (ZPP);
- The specifications for the selection of the collaborative robot are:
 - Reaching > 1000mm;
 - Low Payload (<10kg);
 - Tool changer (the robot will need different tools for grasping and other tasks like spraying, cleaning, holding parts, etc.).
- The specifications for the transportation system (AGV/mobile robot):
 - Lifter for placing the parts over the conveyor;
 - Docking Mechanism to grant accurate positioning;
 - Tool changer.

Figure 22. Logistic Station - Conceptual Layout

- A. Warehouse: bins with the raw material
- B. Lightweight robot on a rail (linear interpolated axis)
- C. Wrench Reaction Telescopic Arm (passive handle for a power tool, like a dyno-meter wrench)
- D. AGV (one of a fleet)
- E. Conveyor: passive conveyor, the movement of the ZPP on the surface is manually done by the operator
- F. Bins for tools used by the robot and by the humans, metrological tools,
- G. Part of the conveyor will allow access to the part from 3 different directions, in the case of special needs by the operator
- H. Robot tool warehouse

Figure 23. Logistic Station - Conceptual Layout

Figure 24. Logistic Station – Conceptual Layout (lateral view)

Therefore, as shown in Figure 23, the logistic stations will be composed by the following main components:

- A. *Warehouse*: the bins will store raw materials and items that should be used in the assembly of the pallet. The warehouse should be accessible both to the human and to the robot. The robot should be able to reach every position of the warehouse;
- B. *Lightweight robot on a rail (linear interpolated axis)*: the robot workspace will be increased through a linear axis. Such a solution will allow a more powerful human robot collaboration, and the possibility to install a standard collaborative robot despite its own limited reaching.
- C. *Wrench Reaction Telescopic Arm (passive handle for a power tool, like a dyno-meter wrench)*: the system will be usable both from a human operator or from the robot. A proper coupling between the robot hand and the wrench will be designed. This solution will allow the robot to execute high-torque screwing and bolt tightening, also greater the maximum torque allowed to the robot joint torque.
- D. *AGV (one of a fleet)*: the AGV (mobile robot) will feed the system with the ZPP (zero-point plate) to be assembled/disassembled. The control and motion planning of the manipulator will be according to the functionalities displayed by the standard robot controller. None research activity in such field is foreseen.
- E. *Conveyor (passive conveyor)*: the movement of the ZPP on the surface is manually done by the operator; the conveyor will be a set of passive rolling supports, that allow the movement of the plates (10-15kg) without stress for the operator. The conveyor will be provided by referenced fixtures to block the pallets in a defined set of positions accordingly to the task specification.
- F. *Bins for tools*: the bins will store tools for the robots, tools for the human, fixtures, etc. The bins will be mainly used by the human, but accessible to the robot, especially for dropping tasks.
- G. A section of conveyor will allow access to the part from 3 different directions, in the case of special needs by the operator; the human should be able to move around the conveyor, and the robot should adapt its own behaviour.
- H. *Robot tool warehouse*: a set of tools that can be assembled autonomously by the robot will be available.

Note that some strong assumptions have been taken into account in the conceptual design of the logistic station:

- One human operator at the time will work at the logistic station;
- The conceptual layout will be led by ergonomics evaluation for the human, and the table height (in the figure is 1m), position of the bins with the tool (wrenches, screwdriver, metrological tools) will be properly defined in the next project steps;
- The human will move the metal plates over the conveyor manually;
- The human can access the warehouse as needed;

- The human and the robot will collaborate in placing parts on the nominal positions on the ZPP;
- The human and the robot will collaborate in screwing/unscrewing;
- Physical interaction human robots will be limited while the parallel task would cover the 90% of the actual work;
- The robot should be able to act as an ergonomic handle to the user if the user has to analyse a part (as in quality check operations);
- The robot series of the task will be very large: the robot will clean the parts (pneumatic cleaner) as needed, the robot will assemble parts, the robot will clamp objects;
- The grasping from the bins will be NOT a random bin picking, but all the parts in the bins will be easy to be grasped and manipulated, using simple vacuum-based gripper, and/or standard under-actuated adaptive gripper;
- The voice interaction with the robot is not possible, due to the high volume of noise in the working scene;

Figure 25. Logistic Station Conceptual Layout

Finally, the mandatory requirements will be:

- I. Tracking of the human in the proximity of the station
- II. Tracking the hands, the trunk and the head positions of the human
- III. Gesture recognition
- IV. The natural interaction between human and robot
- V. Safe motion planner
- VI. Optimal and adaptive scheduling according to human needs

3.4.1.2 Use case layout: LUS Station

The LUS station will implement the best of the innovative guidelines for the human-robot safe collaboration when the robot is a medium-high payload robot.

The robot will handle and assemble ZPP with pre-assembled items, of about 20kg plus the gripper weight. The automation and the human robot collaboration will be therefore designed according to the available robotized solution with such payloads. In the following figures, the conceptual layout of the LUS station is shown.

Figure 26. LUS Conceptual Layout, and robot occupation area

Figure 27. LUS - High payload colabrative robot OR robot with safety sensors enabling workspace sharing

Figure 28. Robotized LUS - Conceptual Layout

Figure 29. robotized LUS - Conceptual Layout – mobility of the human and robot

Figure 30. LUS - View from the point of view of the camera system (mounted on the ceiling)

At the D1.2 writing time, in order to mitigate project risk, the assumption is that a non-cooperative (e.g., standard) robot will be integrated.

Therefore, using a standard robot, the collaboration will consist mainly of:

- *No-physical interaction, and only workspace sharing*: such an assumption will allow the autonomous movement of the robot only according to proper risk analysis, and exploiting a redundant safe speed separation monitoring (e.g. redundant human tracking)
- *Serialization of the operations between humans and robots*: in order to avoid narrow interaction, the activation of the different safety configurations should be dynamic and intuitive for the operator
- *Natural HRC*: the robot-human interaction should be natural, exploiting gesture for the activation and de-activation of a series of tasks
- *Simplification of robot work*: the robot tasks will consist of a limited set of functions, mainly the grasping and handling of the ZPP from/to the AGV.

3.4.2 Logistic station workflow

Even if the process workflow at the logistic station can be very variable and several tasks could be performed depending on the specific assembly operation, a common workflow has been identified to define at least an approximative step-by-step sequence of tasks and to better visualize the role of both operator and robot.

Table 9. step-by-step process at the Logistic station

STEP	OPERATOR	OPERATOR or ROBOT	ROBOT
1	/		Select new pallet to be assembled
2	/		Load nominal assembly sequence
3	Confirm/modify sequence and roles		Wait for operator feedback and load a new sequence
4	Start assembly tasks in parallel and/or collaboratively with the robot		Start assembly tasks in parallel and/or collaboratively with the operator
	--- examples of possible tasks to be executed ---		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Removing plastic covers if present - Visual Control - Blocking the fixtures (if spring-based mechanism) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Separation of the components - Insertion of screws and tightening - Placement of fixtures over the ZPP - Blocking the fixtures (if possible through screwer) - Opening the fixtures (if possible through screwer) 	-

STEP	OPERATOR	OPERATOR or ROBOT	ROBOT
	- Opening the fixtures (if spring-based mechanism)	- Blowing to remove surface impurity (air-compressed cleaner) - Surface Drying - Measures though gauges, calibres, dime	
5	Stop the robot to change sub-tasks sequence (if needed)		Wait for operator feedback and load a new sequence
7	Verify assembly conclusion		Pick the elements from the warehouse for the next item preparation
8	Move to zero-point fixture LUS		

3.4.3 Zero-point fixture station workflow

The human mobility inside the shared work area is a fundamental aspect in order to define the workflow of the human and the robot. In Figure 31 a sequence of possible position for the human inside the working area is shown.

Figure 31. LUS possible movements for human and robots

Based on the assumption that the human can cross the working area asynchronously with the robot, and the robot can stop safely, the workflow for the actual operations at the LUS are listed in the table below.

Table 10. step-by-step process at the LUS station

STEP	OPERATOR	ROBOT
1	Go to LUS	Move metal plates to LUS
2	/	Load nominal tasks sequence
3	Confirm/modify sequence and roles	Wait for operator feedback and load a new sequence
		Position metal plates on the pallet
	Insert hydraulic fixture	
4	Perform quality check	
6	Close hydraulic fixture	Perform quality check
8	Verify correct pallet fixture	Signal the conclusion of the task sequence

3.4.4 Modules involvement

Each module role in the considered use-case is described in the following table.

Table 11. modules involvement in CEMBRE use-case

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#1	CNR	The module will provide a virtualization (i.e., an abstract representation in the Knowledge Base) of the working cell, i.e., of the overall workflow, the possible actions the human can do (described above) and the distribution of elements (position of tools, sensors, types of structure...). All the above information are expected to be defined by a production engineer. Dynamically, the module will keep updated the KB according to the actual operational context.
#2	RWTH	A general semantic cognition method will be developed, which enables the vision network to detect certain objects and classify them using a unique identifier. In case of the Cembre use-case the network will be trained to detect all relevant dynamic objects: human shapes, robots, palletes, metal plates, ZPP and relevant items of the LUS. Further, the static environment will be clustered and classified in conveyors, machines, work stations and room features. All operations are performed and forwarded with the required accuracy to be used in the high-level tasks.

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#3	EURECAT	<p>A human tracking algorithm will be developed to provide information about the workers over time. That means that a skeleton representing the human pose will be obtained as well as the human position within the environment. This module must be able to detect not only the position and pose but also if more than one operator is in the station. The input of this module will be given by a set of sensors placed appropriately around the workplace. The output of this module will be used to define safe working zones for the robot and an input to primitives to recognize human tasks. This module will not be applied to the LUS Station if no cameras are placed (to be defined), while its role will be essential in the Logistic station to allow HRC through different tasks.</p>
#4	TUDA	<p>The Motion Primitives Learning will be a task-agnostic tool. The module will be able to segment monitored operator trajectories and build generalizable motion primitives from this segmented trajectories.</p> <p>In the CEMBRE use case, the module will build motion primitives based on the gestures of the human. These motion primitives could be used afterwards to classify and predict a wide set of human gestures characterizing the use-case tasks.</p>
#5	EURECAT	<p>This module will develop the necessary algorithms to interpret data coming from the workspace monitoring and cognition in order to identify the task that the worker is executing and to provide this information to the dynamic task planning and scheduling algorithm. That means that the output from Primitives Learning and Environment Cognition will be used as input to create a solution which is able to do task identification. This module will not be applied to the LUS Station as no task recognition is required, while it will be fundamental in the Logistic station to recognize a wide set of operator tasks, understand which step of the process is and reschedule dynamically the workflow, since there is no a well-defined sequence in that workstation.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#6	CNR-ISTC	<p>In the CEMBRE pilot, the module will work at two different, yet connected, levels. In general, the module will dynamically generate a task plan in order to assign production tasks. Then, it will monitor tasks execution and, in case of need, it will adapt execution and/or revise tasks assignment in order to maintain safety and increase efficacy. At a first level, the task planning system will coordinate the shopfloor activities, coordinating the task among different stations and addressing resources allocation. At a second level, in a specific robotic LUS, the task planning system will coordinate human and robot activities assigning tasks among them and guaranteeing to minimize the cycle time as well as keep the operator safe. The task planning will take care to internally manage production goals and dispatch tasks allocation among different stations.</p> <p>The probabilistic reasoning sub-module will use some of the pieces of information saved in the Knowledge Base about the actual status of the system (the inputs) to derive decision values and predictions (the outputs) that will be used as triggers for the main planner. Furthermore, the parallel planning feature with its according smoothing algorithms will ensure at each time step that a valid plan is available for the actors.</p>
#7	CNR-STIIMA	<p>The online/offline motion planner will be a task-agnostic tool. In other words, once the digital model of each task will be available, the modules will act in order to ease and optimize the robot plans given the task constraints and goals.</p> <p>The offline motion planner will ensure the intuitive easiness granting collision free and ergonomics trajectories. The online motion planner will allow the reaction to the dynamic environment according to the data coming from the tracking system.</p> <p>In the CEMBRE environment, the robot dexterity and manipulability will be of utmost importance.</p> <p>The high variability of tasks and combinations of tasks between human and operator will be a challenge for the off-line module planner and for the online re-planner.</p> <p>Different strategies will be investigated, both model based and based on deep-learning (reinforcement learning) in order to be able to smooth select the best trajectory according to the changing environmental condition.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#8	TUDA	<p>The Learning from Demonstration (LfD) is an alternative way of path planning. In LfD, the operator could teach the robot the correct path to follow and robot would build motion primitives in order to follow correctly taught motions.</p> <p>In the CEMBRE use case, due to the high variability of the tasks, the LfD could be applied as an alternative to the offline path planner in order to teach to the robot the motion it should follow.</p>
#9	LMS	<p>Human operator involvement is critical in this use case. Thus, simple and easy to use interfaces for the interaction between the worker and the rest SHAREWORK system will be deployed. The operator will wear a pair of AR glasses which will provide information for the workflow in each station. Additionally, online re-scheduling of the executed tasks and direct control of the robot (start/ stop) will be provided.</p>
#10	FRAUNHOFER	<p>There must be a separation between logistic area and assembly area with different requirements to the access for workers in this area. The robot must operate with a safe velocity while moving in the collaborative area (preparation-area and assembly in LUS system). There must be a force control implemented in the robotic system in case of an unexpected contact between human and robot. for the gripping task the force should be supervised by the robotic system. In case of moving the high-payload parts it should not be possible for a human to reach the robot. This can be done by task separation and optical sensors.</p>
#11	RWTH	<p>The TCP vision system will be integrated in the overall vision network of module #2 to enable further surveillance of the workspace. The system is projected to improve the reliability of surveillance of the human worker during mounting operations inside the car. Further, this module adapts the safety system based on module #10 onto the local robot frame to improve the safety of the human worker.</p>
#12	INTRA	<p>This module will be generic and applicable to all use cases. In particular this module will deliver a toolset for data security. Each use case will be able to select and apply the useful and relevant components. The toolset will provide both data security Policies and Practices as well as a list of software libraries and tools.</p>
#13	FRAUNHOFER	<p>The system can check if the operator is in a bad ergonomic posture and provide this information to the worker for him to be able to correct tposture. There must be 2 systems – one for the preparation-area and one for the LUS assembly.</p>

MODULE ID	RESPONSIBLE	EXPECTED ROLE IN THE USE CASE
#14	LMS	In order to familiarize new operators with the process, a training AR application will be provided. This application will introduce to the operators in a palatable way the SHAREWORK solution, guiding them in the execution of the collaborative process.

3.5 Modules specifications

Within this paragraph, specifications of each Sharework module specifications are described in terms of sensors to be used, interdependency with other modules (both for input and output), tasks to be performed in the Sharework system (independently from the use-case). Furthermore, specific application in each use-case is detailed depending on end-user needs and objectives.

3.5.1 Knowledge Base

This module aims at defining and implementing a knowledge base (KB) to represent the definition of human tasks, robot tasks, relations among tasks (tree of tasks for task precedence constraints or task simultaneous execution for collaborative tasks), identification of possible cooperative modes and possible system failures (e.g., breakdown of the robot, missed grasping, etc.) and general environmental information perceived. The KB will be defined pursuing an ontological approach aiming at characterizing general properties and features of the collaborative application scenarios. The Ontology (TBox) will characterize the experience and a prior/static known features of the production processes (process structure in terms of tasks and operational requirements) and capabilities of the involved actors (i.e. the robot and the human operator). The envisaged Ontology will be designed by extending DOLCE, a foundational ontology which represents a well suited formal basis. The concrete extension of such ontology will be supported by common ontological frameworks such as, e.g., Protégé. Given such ontology, a specific KB will be instantiated (ABox) in order to instantiate the TBox and then model the particular to be considered. Thus, the KB will include also information related to sensing knowledge defined in Module 2. The KB will include also a decomposition of each task in primitives and the consistency check before the possible allocation to the robot (taking into account payload, reachability, and tool). Regarding human behaviour, in addition of containing human and robot motion primitives, the KB will also include addition information about, e.g., ergonomics of human operators (Module 3), tasks (composed separate motions to different models) and objectives (shape, weight, physical properties) that completely describe human behaviour which will later be used for the identification of HR and operator tasks (Module 3).

This task is to design the knowledge processing mechanisms and the inference rules needed to process real data coming from the environment (Module 2) and build an abstraction of the production scenario. Inference rules to recognize events occurring as well as activities and production tasks in execution by the shopfloor and/or operators. This task will implement a process interacting with the different sub-systems (environment cognition, dynamic planning, robot controllers, dynamic safety engine, etc.) through events management (e.g., continuous pooling/publish-subscription) and read/write data on KB. The KB will be then continuously maintained and refined by means of knowledge processing mechanisms capable of managing

sensor data and inferring additional knowledge if possible. The needed data processing and inference mechanisms will be developed by leveraging inference API like Apache Jena, or existing ontology reasoners like Pellet or Hermit.

In general the KB will act as a information repository server for all the other modules.

3.5.2 *Environment Cognition*

Within ShareWork project, a general semantic cognition method will be developed, which enables the vision network to detect certain objects and classify them using a unique identifier. For classification machine learning approaches will be used. These algorithms have to be taught on the specific use –case in order to achieve a satisfactory level of confidence. Therefore, this module requires training data from the different use case owners.

The vision system will be set up in such a way, that the field of vision is blocked as less as possible. In order to allow a certain level of reliability and redundancy even in case of occlusion, the system is projected to cover the desired objects with at least two different sensors. This module has high requirements regarding resolution and accuracy of the classified and segmented objects, as these are used in high-level tasks.

The main adjustment for each use case is the set of detectable objects, which are stated below:

- In the Goizper use-case the required objects are human shapes, robots, bolts, the riveting and adhesive tools and the electrical screw driver, rotary tables, work benches and general room features.
- In the Alstom use-case the required objects are human shapes, robots, door and window frames, rivets (including their mounting state), the silicon gun and riveting tools, work tables, work benches and general room features. This case has a high demand on the vision system resolution due to large measurement distances.
- In the Nissan use-case the required objects are human shapes, robots, chassis and doors, conveyor section, feeding conveyor and room features.
- In the Cembre use-case the required objects are human shapes, robots, palettes, metal plates and relevant items of the LUS, conveyors, machines, work stations and room features.

3.5.3 *Human Tracking*

A human tracking algorithm will be developed to provide information about the workers over time. That means that a skeleton representing the human pose will be obtained as well as the human position within the environment.

The input of this module will be given by a set of sensors placed appropriately around the workplace. The main source will be cameras, mainly 3D cameras, since it is necessary to have the information of the human position in real coordinates, not just the image. Other types of sensor will be used if they are considered necessary.

This module can be treated in a generic way, regardless of the use case. That means that in all use cases it is important to determine the 3D position of the humans so that the robot can interact with them depending on where they are. It is for this reason that the proposed solution will not depend on the use case. Once we apply the module to a use case, the workplace and specific characteristics will be analysed to propose the best combination of sensors in order to be able to track humans properly. That implies that it is possible to find different sensors between use cases to reach all the requirements regarding precision and quality.

We need to mention two considerations: it is possible that in some actions in different use cases a hand tracking will be necessary apart from body tracking, which will mean that a greater precision will be necessary when doing the analysis. Moreover, the main problem this module will face will be human occlusions. It is important to define sensor positions so that the operator is never located in a blind zone for all cameras as this may mean that some specific actions will be difficult to track. Special analysis will be done to solve that kind of problems.

This is what will be done in the different use cases:

- In the GOIZPER use case, the module will be applied to track all human actions in the three processes which have been defined: bolts tightening, locking ring bolts tightening and visual inspection.
- In the ALSTOM use case, the module will track humans in the main tasks which have been defined: surface cleaning, silicone spreading and rivets positioning.
- In the NISSAN use case, the module will be used to track the operator in the whole door assembly process. It may be useful to track not only the body but also the hands to have specific information which will be used in the task recognition.
- In the CEMBRE use case, the module will have to track humans in their main tasks which have been defined in the assembly area. The application of the module to the LUS station is not defined at this moment as we don't have a final decision.

3.5.4 Primitives Learning

The aim of this module will be to develop algorithms that are able to extract the informative and meaningful primitives from human monitored tracking systems. The system should be able to detect the relevant segments of the trajectory and build a generalizable trajectory representation from each of the segments. Also, in front of partial information of a trajectory, the system should be able to predict how the trajectory will end up, using previous information.

The algorithm will receive human motion tracking system information and environment segmentation information. From here, the primitives learning module should be able to first segment this unlabelled trajectories into meaningful segments. Then, each of the segment should be comprised into a motion primitive that would normalize in time the segment and generalize. The obtained primitives segments will be used as input for both the classification process of the tasks and also as human workspace cognition for safe robot motion planning.

In particular the motion primitives module will be applied for different goals in each use case:

- In the GOIZPER use case, the module will be applied in order to extract the primitives of the user operators performing bolt tightening and assembly task. Together with the classification module, the module will help to identify operator actions.
- In the ALSTOM use case, the module needs to build motion primitives on the actions that the operator performs such as cleaning surface, spreading silicone, positioning rivets or fixing structure. This information will be useful for classification of the operator tasks but also to plan safe robot motions.
- In the NISSAN use case, the module needs to build probabilistic motion primitives that could inform the robot's motion planners what is the human's workspace. This Motion Primitives integration in the Path Planning will ensure safety in the workspace.
- In the CEMBRE use case, the module will build motion primitives based on the gestures of the human. These motion primitives could be used afterwards to classify and predict human gestures.

3.5.5 Human Task Identification

The aim of this module will be to develop the necessary algorithms to interpret data coming from the workspace monitoring and cognition in order to identify the task that the worker is executing and to provide this information to the dynamic task planning and scheduling algorithm. That means that the output from Primitives Learning and Environment Cognition will be used as input to create a solution which is able to do task identification.

In this module, the algorithm will be thought and developed in a general way, independently from use cases. A complete list of tasks from all use cases will be elaborated and the final solution will consider all of them. Once we apply the module to a specific use case, only those actions related to it will be considered to increase performance as actions will differ depending on the use case. This guarantees that the solution is sufficiently generic but at the same time it is scalable to be adapted to each use case.

Specifically, analysing the different use case:

- In the GOIZPER use case, the module will be applied to identify tasks related with all the three processes which have been defined: bolts tightening, locking ring bolts tightening and visual inspection.
- In the ALSTOM use case, the module will detect the main tasks which have been defined: surface cleaning, silicone spreading and rivets positioning.
- In the NISSAN use case, the module will be used to detect all tasks related with the whole door assembly process.
- In the CEMBRE use case, the module will have to detect main tasks which will have been defined in the assembly area. This module will not have any application on the LUS station as no human task recognition is required.

3.5.6 Human Aware dynamic planning and scheduling for HRC Tasks

A human-aware dynamic task planning and scheduling framework for human-robot collaborative scenarios in ShareWork will be implemented upon an original flexible task planner, called PLATINUm¹, and leveraging the APSI-TRF framework², a timeline-based planning software infrastructure developed by ISTC-CNR for the European Space Agency and deployed in several real space missions.

The current system is composed by a timeline-based planner and a knowledge engineering environment to facilitate its use. In ShareWork, PLATINUm will be further advanced in several directions: including functionalities aimed at facilitating the use of the Dynamic Task Planner adapting solutions to different users (through the use of User Profiling), reconciling different competing or simply alternative goals at shop floor (through Goal Reasoning) and automatically improving the adherence of domain modelling (Knowledge Inference).

The ShareWork human aware task planning system will integrate a control architecture for continuous task synthesis, guaranteeing safety critical properties at execution time, and user modelling ability for adapting tasks to the particular human at work and to, e.g., his/her level of attention and stress.

¹ <https://github.com/pstlab/PLATINUm>

² <http://mexar.istc.cnr.it/apsi/>

The probabilistic reasoning sub-module will take pieces of information from the Knowledge Base and transform them in decision values and predictions to be used in the CNR- ISTC planner. In such a way values for the planning predicates are set or re-planning or the activation of special working modes of the robots (AGVs or serial manipulators) are triggered.

Another feature that will be tested separately from the CNR-ISTC planner is the Parallel Planning feature. Parallel to the main plan secondary plans will be generated each couple of seconds/minutes. In case that the main plan cannot be followed and there is no time for re-planning, special transition algorithms will ensure the change to one of the secondary plans.

Specifically, for each use-case:

- In the GOIZPER, ALSTOM and CEMBRE use-case the reasoning submodule will be applied to generate decision values and predictions based on the task that the human is doing, the position of the human, the position of other elements (tools, bolts, screws etc.), the tasks that the human should execute and the commands that the robot is receiving from the human. The parallel planning feature will be tested for the cases when the original plan is not followed anymore for example because the human is not executing its assigned task anymore, new commands are passed to the robot etc.
- In the NISSAN use-case neither the uncertainty reasoning sub-module nor the parallel planning will be used due to the exact sequence of actions that must be done under strict temporal constraints.

3.5.7 *Offline and real-time human aware and safe robot motion planning*

The Offline and real-time human aware and safe robot motion planning will integrate different motion planner to allow a simple, fast and safe motion planning inside the operative scene.

The specifications from the end user will consist of:

- The 3D model of the environment,
- A formalized task description, and constraints between the tasks
- The robot selected should support a ROS communication interface that allows the streaming of the points, and the remote modification of the velocity (speed override) as needed

This module will contribute to meet the end user's requirements from a different perspective. First the off-line motion planning will ease the programming phase, in every working conditions, also for the definition of very free-collision complex trajectory. While the online re-planning will strengthen the robustness of the use case and the productivity for the application scenario.

Specifically, analysing the different use case:

- In the GOIZPER use case, the online re-planning is strongly constrained because where the movement is strongly synchronized between a human operator and robot. Therefore, an adaptive, safe and fuzzy velocity tuning is expected to be the most important reaction strategies in the use-case.
- In the ALSTOM environment, the robot tasks are almost all constrained in the Cartesian space, therefore the room for online re-planning is limited. Furthermore, the synchronization between the human operator and the robot is still to be further

investigated. Therefore, the application key will be to grant the best motion planning offline, with a limited online adaptation.

- In the NISSAN environment, the robot dexterity and manipulability will be of utmost importance. Indeed, the object to be manipulated together with the grasping system displays a large footprint with respect to the robot dimension. Therefore, online re-planning may be difficult due to the cluttered operative scene. Therefore, an adaptive, safe and fuzzy velocity tuning is expected to be the most important reaction strategies in the use-case.
- Finally, in CEMBRE both the off-line modules and the online modules will be useful in order to deal with the complexity and asynchronistic execution of the tasks.

3.5.8 Robot Motion Planning based on learning from demonstration

Learning from Demonstrations provide an alternative tool to path planning. In situations in which the path planning is quite hard in the classic methods, Learning from Demonstration could be a nice tool to learn a correct robot motion plan. The system should provide the possibility to teach to the robot the path to follow by manual guidance.

In a more complex scenarios, Learning from Demonstrations would provide the initial motion to follow and the robot should improve over the learned motion applying reinforcement Learning.

If enough demonstrations have been provided, the system could learn to generalize the learned motions to new situations.

In particular on each use case this module could be applied in:

- In ALSTOM use case, robot tasks such as sillicon appliance and riveting can be easily taught using LfD.
- In the NISSAN use case, the LfD could be applied as an alternative path planner on which the robot is taught by manual guidance the correct path to follow and the robot imitates and improves his motion until the door is correctly fixed.
- In the CEMBRE use case, due to the high variability of the tasks, the LfD could be applied as an alternative to the offline path planner in order to teach to the robot the motion it should follow.

3.5.9 Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication

This module is designed to provide smart solutions for enhancing the interaction of human operators with the rest Sharework system. Augmented reality application running on headset devices and smart screen applications for tablet are some of the designed approaches for publishing information to the works. In terms of collecting information from the users, various functionalities will be exploited. In particular, the interactable holograms of an AR application, simple voice commands and operator's hand gestures are the main functionalities for communicating with the Sharework system.

As is presented in the module deployment diagram shown in Figure 32, the developments of this module are closely related with the modules for robot planning, human detection and human task identification. An interface with the robot is required for providing crucial

information to the operator. In this way the human workers will be aware of what the robot is doing, thus it will be easier to establish a human robot collaboration. Regarding the connection with the human oriented modules, the operators will be alerted in case they have a bad posture while working over a long period of time and through the same interface important information for the tasks that are assigned to him/her will be visualised. A gesture detection component will provide an additional approach for taking input from the human user.

Figure 32. Module 9 deployment diagram

More specific, based on the use case requirements the initial design of direct and natural human-system and system-human communication module contains the following components

- **Screen applications:** Intuitive and easy to use applications for tablets, smartphones and PCs will be delivered within this component. The goal is to make these applications easy to integrate and deploy in all cases, for this reason they will be based on web technologies. An interface with Robotics Operating System (ROS) is required as the rest modules will be built on top of this framework.
- **AR application:** An AR application designed and developed for Microsoft HoloLens will be delivered. Users will be able to exploit all the advanced features that Augmented Reality provides, such as click on virtual buttons and inspect holograms of process parts. Additionally, voice commands will be used in the use cases that allows it, depending on the noise of the workspace.
- **Gesture detector:** An individual component will be delivered as a software for detecting a set of trained gestures command. A machine learning approach will be used in order to encounter accuracy issues that may appear depending on operator's body shape. Human tracking module will feed with the detected human data the gesture component

3.5.10 Human safety in HRC tasks with collaborative and high-payload robots

This module aims to ensure safety of operator during human-robot cooperative tasks, even in case of cooperation with high-payload standard industrial robot. Safety in HRC mainly concerns with the avoidance of any unintentional and potentially dangerous collision between robot (intended as robot itself but also end-effector) and operator. Therefore, this module will identify any possible countermeasure to fully satisfy all safety requirements, but at the same time without penalizing too much operator freedom of movement and process cycle time.

Inputs required by this module mainly come from Human Tracking module (the system has to know in each moment where the operator is to plan the robot motion in a safe way) , Environment Cognition module (to have a general knowledge of other element e.g. tools present in the environment) and also human aware robot motion planning. Module #11 will provide the safety system with event generation in case of implausible system situation to ensure overall reliability of the environment cognition.

The main countermeasures which will be adopted within the Sharework system are valid for all the four use-cases and they will foresee:

- Decrease of robot speed to a safe value (< 250 mm/s) for all the collaborative tasks;
- Implementation of a monitoring system (e.g. Kuka SafeOperation) for safe workspace observation;
- Implementation of methods to ensure safety when performing force control;
- Direct collaborative operation of the robot only allowed with 1 worker.

These measures are fundamental to make possible a safe and effective HRC even with high-payload standard industrial robots and it is essential within the project since at least three use-cases will use them for the respective application. Furthermore, additional safety measures will be assessed for each specific use-case and task to minimize the risk.

3.5.11 Tooling Sensors adaption for safe HRC

This module has two major tasks: First by developing methodologies, which ensure plausibility of the overall sensor system by appending the vision system with TCP camera and second by adapting the safety system methodology to the local robot frame.

The TCP vision system will be integrated in the vision network established by module #2, enabling further surveillance in otherwise blocked areas, e.g. in car handling. Adding another sensor contributes to the redundancy and overall reliability of the environment cognition.

The input to this module comes from Module #2, #3, #6,#8 and provides output to Module #10 and #9

Some use-cases establish special needs for local cognition, even when global view is available:

- In Goizper, the screws and their placement in the holes needs to be assured by a local camera to ensure safe collaboration
- Alstom requires additional safety in the rivet state
- Nissan requires a local high resolution view to ensure safety during door assembly
- The Cembre use-case establishes vision blocked areas on the LUS, and requires local perception in the highly payload industry robot

Further, the TCP vision system is used to adapt the safety system from module #10 from the environment to the local robot frame. This allows even safer working conditions for the human workers and enables faster cycle times, due to reduced high risk zone which needs to be analysed. There are similar requirements for the local safety system in all use-cases.

3.5.12 Data security

The Data Security module will develop a specific security policy and prescribe policies for the communications and operations management, as well as access control policies to fortify the overall information security of the system.

These policies will be the result of a dedicated and diligent analysis of the involved systems. The aim of the aforementioned policies will be to mitigate the identified potential threats related to privacy, identity and integrity in order to provide an adequate level of security. Effectively the developed data security module will be a toolset. This toolset will provide both data security Policies and Practices as well as a list of software libraries and tools that will aim to increase the data security of the software systems. The toolset will be generic and potentially applicable to all use cases and modules. Use case developers and module developers will be able to select and apply tools and policies to fortify the data security where needed. For instance module #13 “Continuous Evaluation of Human Ergonomics and Posture Correction” handles sensitive information that require data protection. In particular, module #13 will utilize and process data coming from cameras that have private information of the workers. In this case the Data Security Module will provide data security policies and a list of tools that will be used in order to make sure that that are handled by are secured. In a similar fashion the Data Security toolset will be available to other module developers, to be applied where needed.

3.5.13 Continuous *evaluation of Human ergonomics and posture correction*

This module aims to improve the overall ergonomics in the system. It is realised in two main steps: 1) Continuous Evaluation Alerts and 2) Overall Session Alerts. The Continuous Evaluation alerts, would take input from Module #2, #3, #5, #7 with an approximate period of switching between two major tasks or a minimum of 120 seconds and provide output to module #9 informing about any possible improvement for the next process cycle. The Overall Session Alerts takes inputs from Module #2, #3, #5, #7 over the complete session in a day using analytic diagrams to provide the individual overall analysis for the session for one worker at module #9 using a simple graphical interface on a screen, to ensure improvements for the next day session. Main focus is provided to the posture correction, which can be easily impacted to have better ergonomics.

- In Goipzer Use case, the upper body and spine posture of the worker, placing screws for assembly or performing quality assurance (checking dimension deviations of input shaft) while the robot perform the task would be analysed continuously and alerted for posture correction when needed.
- In Alstom Use case, similar method would be done for respective worker task.
- In Nissan Use case, though most challenging, the upper body during guiding the door as correct position would be analysed for continuous evaluation (especially door positioning and screwing).
- In Cembre use case the upper body particularly the arm position would be analysed during each of the worker tasks to alert for any possible improvements. The assembly of metal parts close to the machine would be a critical event too, because of ergonomically bad postures as a result of the tight assembly space because of the dimensions of the human-machine-interface.

The Overall session Alert would be generated based on the number of individual continuous alerts which would be generated to provide an global information about the total alerts, which need to be taken care and improved for each individual worker (regarding to worker profiles).

3.5.14 Operator training through VR

For the introducing a new operator into the production process and for training activities an AR application for Microsoft HoloLens will be developed. This application will be deployed either “offline” on a mock-up workstation that will be designed only for training purposes or “online” on the real production area. In the following figure are represented the existing state of similar

approaches of AR applications. The module supports two modes: the training mode, where it describes each step of the process utilizing graphical content and step by step instructions on how to proceed, and the assistive mode, where it detects the elements of the real world combined with the expected actions to be performed so the operator knows clearly how to proceed with the task. Human related barriers will be investigated through various surveys for increasing the performance and the usability of the application. This module will be demonstrated in:

- Goizper use case: In this case there are plenty of steps that needs to be memorized from the operator of the workstation (e.g. the precise locking procedure).
- Nissan use case: For this case even if the human operator tasks seems to be easy to remember, the training application will make the robot procedure more comprehensive to the operator.
- Cembre use case: In order to familiarize new operators with the process a training AR application will be provided. This application will introduce to the operators in a palatable way the SHAREWORK solution.

Figure 33. Existing AR applications for training

4 Conclusions

In this document SHAREWORK framework hardware specifications have been reported. A detailed description of the implementation in each use-case is provided by means of graphic representations and tables, highlighting main features, such as shared workspace and timing, of the foreseen human-robot cooperation through all the considered tasks.

Furthermore, a general overview of all modules belonging to the SHAREWORK system is given, defining specifications and inter-modules dependencies, but also specific module application in each use-case is explained to define respective tasks to be done and objectives to be achieved.

The present deliverable will be a solid basis for next documents, in particular D1.5 “Design of the robotic system hardware and architecture”, and in general for the development of the whole SHAREWORK solution.